

Strategic plan 2026-2028

Information & Openness focal area

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1. Introduction

This document presents the 2026-2028 strategic plan for the Information & Openness (I&O) focal area at the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University. The strategic plan explains how we contribute to the overall mission of CWTS and delineates the focal area's vision, objectives, and expected results.

This plan serves as a framework to guide our activities, to inform decisions about which new projects and collaborations to pursue, and to assess our progress. It is structured using a “goal tree” model, moving from an overarching vision to strategic and more concrete operational objectives, to examples of results and projects. This structure ensures coherence between our focal area's aspirations and its actions.

This plan was developed over an ten-month period, in which the focal area collaboratively brainstormed where we would like to go and what we would like to achieve in the coming three years. The focal area coordinators summarized the group's input and presented versions of the strategic plan to the focal area members for iterative development. The plan was then further discussed with the other focal area coordinators and the CWTS Board.

We begin by outlining our overarching *vision*, which describes our long-term ambitions and sets the direction for where we want to go in the coming three years. We then outline high-level *strategic objectives*, which describe the ideal effects we aim to achieve and our contributions to the broader research system. *Operational objectives*, defining concrete actions that will deliver short-term effects in support of the strategic objectives, are then presented. Finally, we provide examples of *results* illustrating tangible outcomes in our descriptions of each operational objective. The vision and strategic objectives are intended to remain stable throughout the period, while operational objectives and results may evolve as projects develop.

2. Vision

The below vision for the I&O focal area describes our long-term ambition and ultimate purpose of our work:

Make open research information the norm. By using trustworthy data sources committed to openness, we strive to remove legal, technical, and social barriers to accessing and reusing research information. This fosters transparent and inclusive use of research information and improves how science is studied, governed, and practiced.

This vision addresses a fundamental challenge in today's research system: the lack of openness in *research information*. Research information — which describes research outputs, activities, and actors — is essential to understand how science operates, how knowledge is produced, and how research systems evolve. It is also critical for shaping policies, evaluating performance, and ensuring accountability in science. Despite its importance, much of this information remains locked in closed and proprietary systems, creating barriers to using this information. These barriers restrict the possibility to study the research system in a comprehensive way, to make well-informed decisions about its governance, and to ensure fairness and equity in access to information and participation in decision-making processes.

This vision also highlights how *open research information* (ORI) can transform this situation. ORI not only helps make research assessment more transparent and responsible, but it also contributes to developing a more inclusive understanding of what is happening in the research system. By removing barriers and promoting openness, we enable diverse stakeholders such as researchers, institutions, policymakers, and society at large to engage with science in a more democratic and equitable way.

This vision is therefore not isolated but is deeply connected to the broader mission of CWTS and is foundational to the other two focal areas, Evaluation & Culture and Engagement & Inclusion. Together, these three focal areas strengthen CWTS's commitment to improving how science is practiced and governed and how it serves society.

3. Strategic objectives

The above vision provides the foundation for our strategic objectives, which define the ideal effects we aim to achieve and indicate what the focal area will contribute to in the broader research system. Our three strategic objectives are to:

A. Establish CWTS as a leading expert center on ORI by developing and sharing critical, comprehensive knowledge on ORI

B. Strengthen the reliability of ORI sources in terms of usability, completeness, accuracy, and sustainability

C. Enable research evaluation and monitoring based on ORI

Strategic objective A: Establish CWTS as a leading expert center on ORI by developing and sharing critical, comprehensive knowledge on ORI

The landscape of research information is highly complex. There are many different infrastructures and actors involved in providing and maintaining research information. These infrastructures differ in their legal status, funding models, governance structures, objectives, and approaches to long-term sustainability. They also vary in how they collaborate and compete. Understanding these differences and the relationships between infrastructures is crucial, as they influence each other in ways that affect openness, reliability, and accessibility. In addition, multiple infrastructures provide overlapping services or data, which can create inefficiencies but also opportunities for resilience.

We aim to develop a deep, critical understanding of this landscape and share insights that help stakeholders navigate it effectively. In so doing, we aim for CWTS to become an expert center on ORI which facilitates knowledge sharing and exchange. A better understanding of the ORI landscape will also help to make more informed interventions needed to achieve the other strategic objectives.

Strategic objective B: Strengthen the reliability of ORI sources in terms of usability, completeness, accuracy, and sustainability

ORI sources are relatively new compared to their proprietary counterparts, and the ecosystem is continuously evolving. There are important relationships between upstream infrastructures that register persistent identifiers, such as Crossref,

DataCite, ORCID, and ROR; other services such as full-text repositories including preprint servers and institutional repositories; and downstream metadata aggregators like OpenAIRE and OpenAlex. Their accessibility and interactions shape the quality and completeness of ORI and determine how well these sources can serve research and policy needs.

Metadata completeness, metadata accuracy, and coverage of diverse types of research are all critical factors, as is the usability of ORI sources. Yet the full picture is still missing, and many aspects about these factors remain unknown. Addressing these gaps is essential for building trust in ORI and ensuring that it is suitable for various use cases.

We will contribute by systematically evaluating ORI sources and identifying gaps in coverage and quality. We will collaborate with infrastructure providers and other stakeholders to improve usability and reliability, and advocate for governance and funding models that ensure long-term sustainability. Through these efforts, we aim to help shape an ORI ecosystem that is usable, robust, and widely adopted.

Strategic objective C: Enable research evaluation and monitoring based on ORI

Moving away from closed and proprietary systems is essential for creating more transparent and formative assessment practices. By promoting ORI-based approaches, developing tools and methods, and supporting their adoption, we aim to foster evaluation systems that are more context-sensitive and allow for better strategic learning.

This means building infrastructures and analytical capabilities that leverage ORI sources for bibliometric analyses, monitoring, and reporting. ORI enables evaluations that are not only reproducible and verifiable but also aligned with principles of openness and responsible research assessment. Unlike proprietary systems, ORI reduces barriers to access, supports equity in participation, and allows stakeholders to critically examine the data and methods behind evaluations.

4. Operational objectives

Operational objectives translate our strategic ambitions into concrete, actionable steps. While strategic objectives define the ideal effects we aim to achieve, operational objectives focus on the practical activities that will deliver these effects in the short to medium term. They provide clarity on what needs to be done, ensuring that our vision and strategic goals are not only aspirational but also implementable.

Each operational objective is directly linked to one or more strategic objectives:

Operational objectives	Strategic objectives		
	A	B	C
1. Build and cultivate strong (international) relationships with ORI stakeholders	✓	✓	✓
2. Develop a critical understanding of the ORI landscape, including actors, infrastructures, and policies	✓		
3. Provide training and guidance on using ORI effectively	✓		✓
4. Collect and analyze evidence on the benefits and challenges of adopting ORI	✓	✓	
5. Systematically evaluate the coverage and quality of ORI sources	✓	✓	
6. Enhance the usability, completeness, and accuracy of ORI sources		✓	✓
7. Broaden the availability of ORI to include information on diverse actors, activities, and outputs		✓	✓
8. Develop versions of ORI sources tailored for research analytics		✓	✓
9. Support the transition from closed systems to ORI			✓

We briefly describe each of these operational objectives and illustrate them with examples of planned results and projects. The objectives are often complementary and interconnected, and their boundaries are therefore not fixed but rather fluid. We also anticipate that there will be some flexibility in the operational objectives

and planned results as we put them into practice. Internally funded research time within the focal area is limited. As a result, meaningful progress toward the operational objectives will need to be achieved predominantly through existing funded projects or by acquiring new externally funded research projects, through service and consulting projects, or by organizing professional courses that directly support one or multiple operational objectives. Strategic and well aligned decisions regarding project acquisition will therefore be essential for realizing this plan.

Operational objective 1: Build and cultivate strong (international) relationships with ORI stakeholders

We aim to strengthen the ORI ecosystem through active collaboration and engagement. This includes contributing to key infrastructures such as Crossref, OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, and ROR; participating in global initiatives like the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, COMET (Collaborative Metadata), and CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment); and contributing to advisory boards and working groups that shape the future of ORI. Members of our focal area are actively involved in several Barcelona Declaration working groups, including in leadership roles. Our engagement also includes participation in the OpenAlex Advisory Board. At the national level, we engage through the SURF Advisory Group on Open Research Information and the OpenAIRE National Membership Consortium, which facilitates Dutch institutions' participation in OpenAIRE. These partnerships allow CWTS to share expertise, influence agendas, and promote openness and sustainability in research information.

Operational objective 2: Develop a critical understanding of the ORI landscape, including actors, infrastructures, and policies

A deep and critical understanding of the ORI landscape, including how ORI is created, managed, and exposed, is essential for shaping effective strategies and interventions. Our work will map relevant relationships between infrastructures and analyze how they collaborate or compete; how policies at institutional, national, and international levels affect ORI adoption; and what governance and funding mechanisms ensure long-term sustainability. Planned activities include exploring what constitutes an open research information infrastructure, conducting comparative analyses of governance and funding models, examining studies on implications of policy frameworks, and formulating evidence-based recommendations for improved sustainability and coordination.

By developing this critical understanding, we will provide actionable insights for stakeholders, support informed decision-making by both users and providers of ORI, inform advocacy for sustainable open infrastructures, and strengthen the

evidence base for transitioning to ORI. Many of the activities under this objective are carried out in the context of the Barcelona Declaration working groups.

Operational objective 3: Provide training and guidance on using ORI effectively

Building capacity to use ORI is essential for its adoption and responsible application. Many stakeholders — researchers, institutions, and policymakers — are still unfamiliar with ORI sources, their benefits, and their limitations. Our goal is to equip these groups with the knowledge and skills needed to integrate ORI into research evaluation, monitoring, and analytics in ways that align with responsible research assessment.

We will achieve this by developing and delivering high-quality training programs, courses, and guidance materials. This includes continuing our established course *Scientometrics Using Open Data*, which introduces participants to ORI-based approaches for scientometric analysis, and expanding offerings to cover tools such as Google BigQuery for large-scale data handling. We also plan to create modular training resources for different audiences, from introductory sessions for newcomers to advanced workshops for technical users.

In addition, we plan to provide tailored guidance for organizations transitioning to ORI, addressing practical challenges such as data integration, workflow redesign, and quality assurance. We anticipate that this guidance will be organized and delivered primarily through service and consultancy projects. These efforts will not only support adoption but also foster a community of practice around ORI, ensuring that stakeholders can make informed decisions and apply ORI responsibly.

Operational objective 4: Collect and analyze evidence on the benefits and challenges of adopting ORI

Understanding the benefits and barriers to adopting open research information is essential for supporting transitions and shaping effective strategies. While ORI offers clear advantages, its adoption can be hindered by technical, organizational, and cultural challenges.

We will systematically collect and analyze evidence on these dynamics through multiple approaches. This includes designing surveys and interviews with institutions and clients that have transitioned to ORI or are considering doing so, as well as conducting longitudinal studies of adoption trajectories. We will examine perceived benefits such as improved transparency and flexibility, cost savings, better interoperability, and enhanced trust, alongside challenges like data quality concerns, integration complexity, and resistance to change.

A key contribution to this objective is an ongoing doctoral research project that investigates adoption and resistance to ORI across different stakeholder groups. This research will provide in-depth insights into motivations, barriers, and strategies for successful implementation. Additionally, we plan to develop case studies of institutions that have completed the transition and comparative analyses of organizations using closed versus open systems.

Findings from these efforts can inform practical guidance for stakeholders, support advocacy for ORI adoption, and feed into communication strategies that articulate the value of ORI and address common misconceptions.

Operational objective 5: Systematically evaluate the coverage and quality of ORI sources

Reliable and comprehensive open research information is the foundation for its adoption and effective use. However, ORI sources vary significantly in terms of completeness, accuracy, and consistency. Without systematic evaluation, stakeholders cannot fully trust these sources for research analytics, monitoring, or policymaking.

Our aim is to develop and apply robust approaches for assessing the coverage and quality of ORI sources. This includes evaluating coverage of research outputs and metadata completeness and accuracy (e.g., author affiliations, cited references, source information, funding information) and consistency across infrastructures. We will also monitor longitudinal changes to track improvements and identify persistent gaps.

Importantly, ORI sources often provide broader coverage than proprietary systems, for example by including preprints, datasets, and other non-traditional outputs. This expanded scope creates significant opportunities for more inclusive and innovative approaches to research evaluation and monitoring. However, leveraging these opportunities responsibly requires a clear understanding of the limitations in completeness and accuracy. Our evaluations will therefore not only identify gaps but also explore how broader coverage can be used effectively without compromising reliability.

Examples of planned activities include continuing our annual analysis of Crossref metadata availability, assessing coverage and metadata quality in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE, and comparing ORI sources to highlight strengths and weaknesses.

Through these evaluations, we will provide evidence-based recommendations to infrastructure providers, support concrete improvements in data quality, and strengthen trust in ORI for diverse use cases. Many of the resulting effects and outcomes will arise directly from interventions, either those initiated by CWTS or

those undertaken collaboratively with infrastructure providers in response to identified gaps.

Operational objective 6: Enhance the usability, completeness, and accuracy of ORI sources

Improving the usability and reliability of ORI sources is critical for their adoption and effective use. While ORI infrastructures provide open access to research information, users often face challenges related to incomplete metadata, inconsistent identifiers, and technical barriers to accessing and processing data. Addressing these issues will make ORI sources more practical for research evaluation, monitoring, and analytics.

We therefore aim to work to actively improve ORI sources. One example of our work in this area is how detecting errors in affiliation data while developing the Leiden Ranking Open Edition led very concretely to improvements in both ROR and OpenAlex. Another stream of our work in this area takes place in the context of COMET, where we contribute to a model that enables stakeholders across the ecosystem to exchange metadata improvements and enrichments at scale. Within COMET, some projects focus on filling gaps in metadata sources such as Crossref and DataCite by linking preprints to their published versions in journals and extracting affiliation information from preprints. COMET also functions as a space for experimentation with AI-driven approaches for producing and evaluating metadata enrichments. In this context, we develop, fine-tune, and apply open-weight models for extraction and classification tasks, with particular attention to transparency, reproducibility, and digital autonomy in the design and deployment of these methods.

Usability in this context primarily refers to how easily users can retrieve and work with ORI data without extensive preprocessing. For example, by making all underlying data of the Leiden Ranking Open Edition available in Google BigQuery, we lower barriers for users, enabling immediate querying in a scalable environment rather than requiring extensive preprocessing. We also participate in ORION-DBS, a growing collection of publicly available datasets hosted by different organizations in Google BigQuery, which supports scalable, open analytical work with ORI sources. Similar initiatives will be pursued to ensure ORI sources are not only open but also more user-friendly for diverse stakeholders.

By contributing to the usability, completeness, and accuracy of ORI sources, we will help ensure ORI sources are robust, user-friendly, and widely adopted, supporting the transition to open and responsible research information systems.

Operational objective 7: Broaden the availability of ORI to include information on diverse actors, activities, and outputs

To enable more comprehensive and inclusive analyses based on ROI, we will work toward expanding the breadth of ORI sources. Together with SURF, we will develop a national infrastructure for ORI, called BROCCOLI, that brings together information on Dutch research actors, activities, and outputs in an open environment. This infrastructure will facilitate evidence-informed decision-making in the Dutch research system by supporting monitoring of publisher deals, open science practices, and responsible research evaluation.

Another stream of work, building on existing work by CWTS researchers, is focused on identifying linkages between ORI sources and other datasets to capture relationships between, for instance, scientific publications on the one hand, and patents and policy documents on the other hand.

By expanding the breadth of ORI, we will support richer and more context-sensitive approaches to research evaluation and monitoring, enabling stakeholders to understand not only scholarly outputs but also the broader societal and economic impacts of research.

Operational objective 8: Develop versions of ORI sources tailored for research analytics

To enable robust analyses using ORI, we will develop enhanced versions of ORI sources that are optimized for research analytics. While ORI infrastructures such as OpenAlex and OpenAIRE provide rich metadata, they are not immediately ready for advanced bibliometric and analytical workflows.

Our work will focus on creating bibliometric-enhanced SQL databases that include works suitable for bibliometric applications. We will distinguish between core and non-core journals and core and non-core publications, create publication-level classifications, and develop approaches for pre-calculated indicators. These enhancements will enable advanced and scalable bibliometric analyses, including the calculation of indicators on citation impact, collaboration, mobility, and open access publishing. These will be supported by a flexible and sophisticated framework of settings, counting methods, and aggregation levels. The Leiden Ranking Open Edition serves as a concrete example of what bibliometrics-ready ORI can achieve.

We also plan to explore the development of an Open Research Intelligence Platform (ORIP), which will combine standardized analytical views on top of ORI data with flexible querying for tailor-made analytical tasks. By creating bibliometrics-ready versions of ORI sources and ORIP, we will support the transition to open and

responsible research analytics, helping to ensure that stakeholders can perform robust analyses without relying on closed and proprietary systems.

Operational objective 9: Support the transition from closed systems to ORI

To support the transition from closed and proprietary systems to ORI, we will provide tools, services, and guidance that enable stakeholders and clients of our services to adopt ORI-based workflows. These services will partly build on our work to improve the accuracy and usability of ORI and to develop research-analytics-tailored versions of ORI sources, which will enable the calculation of advanced bibliometric indicators using flexible and scalable approaches.

We will also develop consultancy trajectories helping organizations design and execute their transition strategies to ORI. Concrete ongoing examples include facilitating transitions for some European universities, as well as for the National Open Research Analytics initiative in Denmark.

We will also continue to work to transition our own work at CWTS to ORI sources by developing a roadmap detailing necessary steps to fully adopt ORI in our research and services. Through these efforts, we aim to reduce dependency on proprietary sources and accelerate the adoption of open, transparent, and responsible research information practices across the ecosystem.

Annual review

We plan to re-evaluate the strategic plan annually in order to make necessary modifications to these objectives as the ORI landscape continues to evolve. Together, these objectives will help to guide our work in achieving the primary ambition of the I&O focal area: to make open research information the norm, rather than the exception.